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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
DOCETAXEL NANOEMULSION****D. Srilatha^{1*}, Dr. CH. Kantlam², M. Navya³, John³, Kutejnaaz³, M. Naresh³, N. Sriya³**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Brilliant College of Pharmacy,
Abdullapurmet Village, Hayathnagar, Rangareddy, Telangana²Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Brilliant College of Pharmacy, Abdullapurmet
Village, Hayathnagar, Rangareddy, Telangana³Department of Pharmaceutics, Brilliant College of Pharmacy, Abdullapurmet Village,
Hayathnagar, Rangareddy, Telangana**Abstract:**

The objective of the present study was to develop and characterize an optimal stable Nano emulsion formulation of Docetaxel with an aim to increase its bioavailability. The components for the formulation of Nano emulsion were olive and olive oil selected as the oil phase, surfactants namely span20 and the co-surfactants, Ethanol were selected. Different concentrations of oil and surfactant, which formed nanoemulsions were selected based on the thermodynamic stability and dispersibility test. Optimized formulation was selected for in vitro study on the basis of higher drug release, optimum globule size, minimum lower viscosity, and overall lower surfactant concentration and co-surfactant. The diffusion of drug from nanoemulsion was compared with marketed formulation and we obtained better result from it. Thus nanoemulsion could be used effectively to improve the bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs to improve their bioavailability. The nanoemulsion were optimized optical transparency, viscosity measurement, phase separation determination of pH, measurement of globule size, zeta potential, drug content, in vitro diffusion study, stability study.

Keywords: Docetaxel, FTIR studies, oils, surfactants, Co-surfactants, In vitro drug release studies

Corresponding author:**D. Srilatha,**Department of Pharmaceutics,
Brilliant College of Pharmacy,
Abdullapurmet Village,
Hayath Nagar,
Rangareddy, Telangana

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1.INTRODUCTION:

Nanoemulsions/Sub-micron emulsions (SMEs)/Mini-emulsions are thermodynamically stable transparent or translucent dispersions of oil and water stabilized by an interfacial film of surfactant and cosurfactant molecules having a globule size of less than 100 nm¹. Recently nanoemulsions are frequently used for delivery of vaccine, DNA encoded drug, antibiotics, cosmetic and topical preparations and are administered via various routes like oral, pulmonary, intranasal, and ocular, and transdermal etc.² Nanoemulsions are categorized as multiphase colloidal dispersion, and are characterized by its stability and clarity. The dispersed phase typically comprises small particles or droplets, and they have very low oil/water interfacial tension.³ Nanoemulsions are formed spontaneously and readily and sometimes generally without high-energy input. In many cases a surfactant or solvent is used in addition to the surfactant, the oil phase and the water phase²⁻⁵ Three types of Nanoemulsions are formed depending on the composition: Oil in water (o/w) , Water in oil (w/o), Bi-continuous In all three types of Nanoemulsions, the interface is stabilized by an appropriate combination of surfactants and/or cosurfactants.⁴The key difference between emulsions and Nanoemulsions are that the former, whilst they may exhibit excellent kinetic stability, are thermodynamically unstable and will eventually show phase separation.⁵Another important difference is their appearance; emulsions are cloudy while Nanoemulsions are clear or translucent. The objective of the present study was to develop and characterize an optimal stable Nano emulsion formulation of Docetaxel with an aim to increase its bioavailability.⁶

Drug excipient compatibility studies⁷

Any potential interaction between drug and excipients can affect the physical or chemical properties of drug, bioavailability and stability of dosage form. Hence, it is important to check and confirm that the selected formulation components are in good compatibility with drug and do not compromise its stability and safety. The principle involved in the IR spectroscopy is measuring the energy difference between the excited and ground states of a molecule. Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis used for identifying the functional groups with their means of attachment thus helps assess the drug excipients interaction in terms of polymerization, cross-linking as well as drug loading in the formulation. FTIR was carried out to evaluate the interaction of excipients with the drug. For pure powdered drug KBR pellet method was used and for physical mixture, polished sodium chloride salt plates were used to check the interaction between the components of the formulation.

2.MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Docetaxel was collected as a gift sample from Hetero labs, Hyderabad and various excipients and polymers were purchased from AR chemicals, Hyderabad.

2.1 METHODOLOGY

Formulation Development Spontaneous Emulsification⁸

Weigh Docetaxel and dissolve it in clove oil. Add Span 20 and PEG 400 to the oil phase. Stir gently or use a vortex mixer to ensure complete dissolution. Use purified buffer (depending on delivery route). Maintain the temperature at room temp (~25°C). Under gentle magnetic stirring (500–1000 rpm), slowly add the oil phase into the aqueous phase. Continue stirring for 15–30 minutes. A translucent or bluish Nano emulsion should form.

Table-1: Composition of Nano emulsion

F. no	Drug	Clove oil	Span 20	PEG	Water
F1	75	5	2	2	Q.S
F2	75	10	4	2	Q.S
F3	75	15	6	2	Q.S
F4	75	20	8	2	Q.S

CHARACTERIZATION^{9,10,11}

pH measurements: The pH is important in case of ophthalmic dosage forms as eyes are sensitive to pH changes and the pH of the prepared Nano emulsions was measured by digital pH meter (DPH 504, Global electronics, India)

Viscosity: The viscosity was measured to determine rheological properties of formulations. Brookfield Rheometer viscometer at 30°C with a CPE 61 spindle at 30 rpm was used to serve this purpose. Results were taken in triplicate and the average was taken in to consideration.

Centrifugation: This parameter was characterized to check the physical stability. The nanoemulsion system was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes to determine whether the system shows signs of creaming or phase separation. The system was observed visually for appearance.

Conductivity: Electrical conductivity of formulated samples was measured using a digital conduct meter at ambient temperature. Results were taken in triplicate and the average was taken in to consideration.

Dilution test: If the continuous phase is added in nanoemulsion, it will not crack or separate into phases. Maximum amount of water and oil were added to o/w and w/o formulations respectively and then inspected visually for clarity and phase separation. Here 50- and 100-times aqueous dilution of the formulation were visually checked for phase separation and clarity. Results were taken in triplicate and the average was taken in to consideration.

Size analysis: The small size of emulsion globules is responsible for its stability and also contributes to the improved ocular absorption. Particularly droplets with Nano size elevate the interfacial area thereby facilitate the drug diffusion to the targeted tissues at greater rates which results in the enhanced clinical efficacy of the drug substance. Hence, it is of utmost importance to verify whether the prepared emulsions are in the required Nano size range or not. Mean globule size, surface charge (Zeta potential) and size distribution of the nanoemulsions (PDI) were determined by photon correlation spectroscopy using a Zetasizer S-90 1000 HS (Malvern Instruments, UK) at 25°C and 90° angle. The samples were prepared by diluting at a ratio of 1:500 with water before the measurement.

SEM Analysis: Morphological evaluation of Docetaxel Nano emulsion was conducted by scanning electron microscopy. The samples were placed over a copper grid coated with carbon film and air-dried, and then were stained with 0.1% phosphotungstic acid. Finally, the samples were air

dried and then observed with an H-7650 Scanning electron microscope.

Drug content: The accuracy of the method of preparation and excipient interference can be predicted by estimating drug content. A small fixed volume of nanoemulsion was taken and diluted with methanol. Then the samples were analyzed by using UV spectrophotometer and the concentrations were calculated from the calibration curve¹².

Diffusion study: The drug release from the NEs was studied by utilizing vertical Franz diffusion cell of 20mm internal diameter and 15 ml receiver capacity. The donor and receiver compartments were separated by the dialysis membrane of 12,000 Da. The dissolution medium, simulated tear fluid (STF) of pH 7.4 was prepared. 1ml of the test formulation was filled in the donor compartment whereas 15ml of the STF was filled in the receiver compartment. 1ml of STF with a dose equivalent amount of drug was served as control. The setup was kept under continuous stirring with a Teflon-coated magnetic bar up on a magnetic stirrer at 100 rpm maintaining a constant temperature of 37±0.5°C. 1ml sample was collected from the receiver compartment and replaced with the same amount of fresh STF at every predetermined time points. The concentration of drug in samples was analyzed using UV¹³.

Stability studies: Storage stability was studied by storing the lyophilized Nanoemulsion samples at 4°C and room temperature for 3 months. In addition, Docetaxel stability in the Nano emulsion was examined by determining the amount of parent drug remaining after specific storage periods.¹⁴

3.RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

FT-IR Spectrum of Docetaxel

Compatibility studies were performed using IR spectrophotometer. The IR spectrum of pure drug and physical mixture of drug and excipients were studied. The peaks obtained in the spectra of each formulation correlates with the peaks of drug spectrum. This indicates that the drug was compatible with the formulation components.

SHIMADZU

Fig-1: FTIR Spectra of Docetaxel

SHIMADZU

Fig-2: FTIR Spectra of physical mixture of drug and excipients

Compatibility studies were performed using IR spectrophotometer. The IR spectrum of pure drug and physical mixture of drug and excipients were studied. The characteristic absorption of peaks were obtained as above and as they were in official limits ($\pm 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) the drug is compatible with excipients.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS:**Table-2: Drug entrapment efficiency of all formulation**

F.no	Drug entrapment efficiency	pH	Viscosity
F1	86.97	5.13	0.769
F2	84.50	4.89	0.738
F3	82.63	5.06	0.755
F4	81.55	5.10	0.752

The entrapment efficiency for the prepared formulation was in the range of 81.55 to 86.97 %. The entrapment efficiency increased progressively with increasing the concentration of oils which could be attributed to the formation of larger nanoemulsion that entrapped more amount of drug. Nanoemulsion were found to be the finest among all with a entrapment efficiency of 86.97. %.

Viscosity

Increase in viscosity can affect the penetration of formulation through skin. Viscosity of formulation is affected by the sonication amplitude. Lower the viscosity better is the permeation. According to our

optimum formulation result viscosity i.e. 0.769 is in good range, so we can assure that our formulation have good permeation due to ideal viscosity range.

pH

pH of formulation has important role for compatibility of formulation with skin. Our formulation has pH value of 4.89 that is compatible to pH of our skin.

Clarity test for NE

Nano emulsions have to be clear in appearance. Formulations we prepared were having difficulty in giving clarity to formulation. Various formulations with different surfactant to oil concentration yielding turbidity except F3 showed little clarity than turbidity so we increased the time of sonication from 10 to 15 minutes and yet not clear. We prepared four more formulations in order to obtain clear results but we changed sonication from continuous to periodic sonication. Periodic sonication yields better result in clarity. It shows that sonication has effect on transparency of Nano emulsion.

Determination of globule size and morphology

sample was coated with gold and allowed the SEM to capture the images at a temperature of - 120°C and voltage of 5kV.

Fig-2: SEM analysis of Optimized Nano emulsion

The SEM photomicrographs of the nanoparticles are shown in Figures, the morphology of the prepared different types of nanoemulsion was found to be almost spherical in shape and have rough surface. The mean particle size of the different formulations of the prepared Nano emulsion was between 125 to 150 nm, it was observed that the particle size increase with increasing in the concentration of oil and surfactant ratio as shown in the formulations that contain the highest ratio of oil.

Fig-3: Particle size analysis of Optimized Nano emulsion

Zeta potential

Fig-4: Zeta potential of Docetaxel nanoemulsion

Table-3: Evaluation Studies of Docetaxel Nano emulsion particle size and Zeta potential

F. No	Particle size (nm)	Zeta potential
F1	125	-29.67
F2	120	-31.20
F3	128	-36.52
F4	126	-35.10

In vitro drug release studies:**Table-4: Results of Docetaxel Nano emulsion of all formulations**

Time(hr.)	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
1	15.69	14.97	16.13	13.24
2	26.90	25.37	27.50	26.87
3	35.78	36.94	34.69	35.46
4	46.93	45.21	45.17	46.82
5	58.90	57.81	55.26	57.84
6	68.49	67.17	65.58	69.10
7	79.63	76.19	72.15	75.46
8	94.25	92.20	93.38	91.20

Fig-5: Drug release studies of (F1-F4) formulations

Among the four types of nanoemulsion highest amount of release percentage i.e., 94.25 % was found for Docetaxel Nano emulsion.

Stability studies

Optimized formulations F1 was selected for accelerated stability studies as per ICH guidelines. The patches were observed for drug release for a period of three months.

Table-5: Stability studies of optimized formulations at $40 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $75 \pm 5\%$ RH for 3 months

Formulation Code	Initial	1 st Month	2 nd Month	3 rd Month	Limits as per Specifications
F-1	94.25	93.67	92.49	91.37	Not less than 85 %
F-1	94.25	93.50	92.15	91.25	Not less than 85 %
F-1	94.25	93.27	92.13	91.05	Not less than 85 %

4.CONCLUSION:

To conclude this study, Formulations with different ratios were prepared with Clove oil as an oil phase and API, the surfactant used as span 20. Purified water was used as an aqueous phase throughout the study. The most compatible NE formulation was

with Span 20 with periodic sonication gave an optimum result among other formulations. This optimum formulation was then tested for its characterization such as droplet size and zeta potential for stability of our Nano emulsion system and was accepted depending on findings and result.

The final formulation as Clove oil-based Nano emulsion for the treatment of cancer, but according to the good results obtained from the whole study, we can ensure the effectiveness of our NE formulation. From above result concluded that Nanoemulsions significantly increase the solubility of Docetaxel, allowing for more efficient drug delivery. Improved bioavailability, Due to the small droplet size and large surface area, Nano emulsions facilitate better absorption, potentially enabling alternative routes of administration. Nanoemulsions can provide sustained or targeted release of Docetaxel, which may reduce dosing frequency and enhance patient compliance. Targeted delivery through Nano emulsions may reduce off-target effects and minimize systemic toxicity.

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